

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE 2 –GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D 8.3: Methodology and training contents based on social impact

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from (October 2024) to (March 2025)
Periodic report date and version:	01/04/2025 version 1
Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	Delivery Date (actual)
D8.1	Waste management in the context of public administration	R	PU	12	18/03/2024	Report containing data related waste management creating public value developed in the frame of the project and prepared from emerging public services practices	04/04/2024
D8.2	Defining clear objectives and measuring them by using appropriate indicators	R	PU	18	30/09/2024	Report containing appropriate indicators related waste management creating public value	03/10/2024
D8.3	Methodology and training contents based on social impact	R	PU	24	31/03/2025	Report containing methodological approach	01/04/2025
D8.4	Case Study applied to waste management	R	PU	28			
D8.5	Urban waste management	R	PU	30			

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art	Report	10 (Gennaio 2024)	04/02/2024	The investigation of the legal framework.		04/02/2024
M2	Defining the main Stakeholder Mapping	Report	12	18/03/2024	The investigation of the Stakeholder Mapping		04/04/2024
M3	Defining the main social impact and measuring public value creation	Report	18	30/09/2024	The investigation of the legal framework		

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

Deliverable D3 entitled "Methodology and training contents based on social impact" is started in October 2024, at the achievement of the D2 named " Defining clear objectives and measuring them by using appropriate indicators".

1.2 Context

The Research Team is composed by Professor Paolo Esposito, Arturo Capasso, Maria Moreno, Riccardo Resciniti, Francesco Rota, Matteo Rossi and Nicola Fontana. Other three Member of the Research Team are: Ahmad Zubair and Ciuffreda Raffaella, Research Fellow.

2. Literature review

A Systematic Literature Review (SLR) summarizes the results of all available studies on a specific topic and provides a high level of evidence. However, Rapid Literature Review (RLR) allow researchers to understand evidence synthesis during which some of the components of the systematic approach are being used to facilitate answering a focused research question.

The literature review on public value aim is to avoid the 'one best way' types of analyses and prescription which dogged early studies in the management field (Hartley et al., 2017; Faulkner & Kaufman, 2018; Bracci et al, 2019). It is useful to ascertain the fluctuation in publication activity (i.e. the number of publications per year), the journals and the authors who made the greatest contribution to the development of the research field in question (i.e. the number of publications per journal and per author). To determine the most published authors, all of them were taken into account, not just the first ones. Then, the citation pattern was highlighted to identify the most influential works and authors. The further stage shifted to the contents of the sample of articles, which were coded according to the seven categories, the selection of which took into account previous similar studies.

1. Type of disclosure, i.e. the area in which falsifications are dealt with.

2. Epistemological orientation, i.e. theoretical or empirical. Theoretical articles, which include literature reviews, are personal analyses and comparisons of positions characterised mainly by the development of hypotheses, opinions. Conversely, if papers aim to refute or confirm existing models and theories, they belong to the second group since they are based on empirical data. They use an inductive approach to provide an interpretation of what is seen. Case studies fall into this category.

3. Methodology, for the purposes of this study, only three macro-groups were identified (qualitative, qualitative, mixed approach). Due to the difficulty of accurately

classifying works considered with a single research method, the choice was made on the three macro-groups mentioned.

4. Theoretical framework and models, i.e. the theory and models on which the studies are based. It is divided into three groups: no proposal, applies or considers previous ones, proposes a new model.

5. Sample, aims to highlight the type of public organisation analysed. Specifically, listed companies were scrutinised.

6. Context, i.e. the regional focus and jurisdiction of the study undertaken. The regional focus is divided into five regions: Europe, North America, Asia, Oceanian and Other.

7. Aims and Key Findings, a category that seeks to identify the research questions and findings of each study to highlight recurring issues.

3. Content Analysis

The study adopted the method of (manual) content analysis on secondary data and, specifically, on conventions and its annexes. Content analysis is a replicable technique for interpreting and decoding a text according to a series of predefined criteria (Weber, 1990; Krippendorff, 2004). Therefore, it is based on the decomposition of the text and in its subsequent re-categorization according to the theoretical dimensions envisaged by the researcher, in order to derive standard models in the presentation and communication of information (Guthrie et al., 2004). Indeed, it has been widely used for the qualitative and quantitative analysis of different types of secondary sources (such as the contract, contract annexes, reports, etc.) related to economic/financial ones (Smith and Taffler, 2000).

Procedures for manual content analysis were used to conduct the study. By recognizing, through a coding procedure, particular qualities of the text and condensing it into many content categories, they let the researcher simply and methodically evaluate vast quantities of data (Neimeyer et al., 1983; Rosenberg et al., 1990; Stemler, 2000).

4. Multiple Case Studies

The nature of the data collected in this study is qualitative. Case study (Yin, 1995; 2009) describe the main characteristics of the phenomena and to explain the dynamics of a specific process. In general, the case study method (Eisenhardt, 1989) is a “bottom-up approach such that the specifics of data produce the generalizations of theory” (p. 547). According to Gustafsson (2017, p.9), the case study “makes to have a deeper understanding of the exploring subject”. Through utilizing a diverse range of data collection and analysis methods, numerous case studies form a research methodology that facilitates the examination of phenomena through context analysis and gathering extensive information (Vindrola-Padros & Johnson, 2020). This methodology effectively provides a deep understanding of the observed phenomenon (Siedlecki, 2020) and aids in bridging the gap between theory and practice.

A deeper comprehension of the phenomena is possible by examining several case studies, which highlight the unique features and aspects of each instance (Goodrick, 2020). Because of its unique characteristics, this qualitative method is frequently employed in the field of business studies and is essential when attempting to explore the dynamics surrounding the development of a particular experience.

6. Triangulation of data

Triangulation of data is necessary since case study investigations technically handle the specific scenario and, as a result, employ different sources of information (Hyer et al., 1999; Flyvbjerg, 2011). In this regard, the data was initially aggregated and subsequently subjected to triangulation. Specifically, the triangulation technique makes it possible to attribute greater credibility, accuracy and validity to the results of qualitative research (Stake, 2000; Creswell, 2007). In fact, the analysis of multiple sources makes it possible to measure the same phenomenon in different ways, thus increasing the value of the results obtained. Indeed, in qualitative research, triangulation represents the equivalent of the reliability tests performed in quantitative research (Creswell, 2007).

In order to correctly conduct a case study, Patton (1987) has identified four types of triangulations. More specifically, these four typologies concern the triangulation of data sources, methods, perspectives on the same data set and between different evaluators. For the purposes of this study, triangulation of data sources and methods was performed. In this regard, first of all, the triangulation of the various sources from which the data was collected was carried out, namely interviews, direct observation of the phenomenon, and the review of documents and information published on the official website and social media channels. In this way, the data were meticulously compared, making it possible to obtain a holistic view of the phenomenon examined and to increase the reliability and credibility of the information collected through the heterogeneous sources. Secondly, the triangulation of the methods, based on the use of different data collection methodologies, made it possible to purify the data from the weaknesses inherent in the individual methods.

7. Conclusion

In conclusion, this research report on "Methodology and training contents based on social impact" has effectively utilized a comprehensive approach to explore the integration of social impact into training methodologies. Through a thorough literature review, we established a foundational understanding of existing frameworks and theories related to social impact. This was complemented by a content analysis that allowed us to scrutinize the specific elements and themes present in current training materials. Multiple case studies provided real-world examples, offering insights into how social impact is implemented in diverse contexts. The triangulation of data from these methods ensured the reliability and validity of our findings, allowing for a robust analysis of the methodologies and content used in training programs focused on social impact. Overall, this research contributes to the development of more effective and socially responsible training programs by highlighting key methodologies and content areas that can enhance social impact.

Last but not least, it was published an article titled “Sustainability in Energy Companies Under the Lens of Cultural Pressures: When Do We Talk of Greenwashing?” on Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, a Class A (Top Journal) Journal by the National Agency for the Evaluation of Universities and Research Institutes (ANVUR).

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